

Effect of aqueous azolla extract and NaCl stress on rice

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We studied the allelopathic effects of *Azolla pinnata* extract on rice seedlings. A 2.5% (wt/vol) extract was prepared by soaking dried azolla in distilled water for 24 h. Five ml azolla extract was added to 0.8% sterilized agar gel with 0, 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6% sodium chloride. Fifty ml of the media was poured in glass bowls. A similar set without azolla extract also was prepared. All treatments were in randomized design with four replications.

Seeds of rice cultivar IR6 were sterilized with 1% sodium hypochlorite for 3 min and rinsed with distilled water. Ten seeds were planted in a circle on the surface of each bowl with

Effect of azolla and salt on germination and seedling growth of rice.^a Sind, Pakistan.

Treatment	Shoot length (cm)	Decrease over control (%)	Root length (cm)	Decrease over control (%)
No azolla, no salt	7.49 a	—	7.31 a	—
Azolla alone	6.67 ab	10.9	4.66 b	36.2
0.2% salt	6.14 a	10.0	7.13 a	2.5
0.4% salt	5.19 c	30.7	6.56 a	10.2
0.6% salt	3.63 d	51.5	5.08 b	30.5
0.2% salt + azolla	6.08 b	18.8	5.31 b	27.4
0.4% salt + azolla	5.27 c	29.6	4.48 b	38.7
0.6% salt + azolla	3.33 d	55.5	2.23 c	69.5

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

the embryo side up and pointing inward. The bowls were covered with petri dishes and incubated at 30 °C for 7 d. Shoot and root lengths were measured. Results are the average of duplicate experiments.

Azolla alone and 0.2% salt alone had no significant effect on seedling growth (see table). But 0.2% salt with azolla extract significantly reduced seedling height. At 0.4 and 0.6%

salinity, a significant reduction in seedling height occurred in all treatments. All salinity levels combined with azolla extract significantly reduced root length. Even azolla alone had significant depressing effect on root growth. The effect of 0.2 and 0.4% salinity alone was not significant.

We concluded that azolla depresses root growth under saline conditions. □

Crop management

Physiological characteristics of seedlings grown in dry-wet nursery (DWN)

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A flexible dry-wet method of raising rice seedlings developed for rainfed regions of Guizhou Province, China, could be adapted for areas where water deficit affects seedling growth and development.

We evaluated physiological differences of seedlings grown in dry-wet nursery (DWN), wet nursery (WN), and dry nursery (DN) in the greenhouse. Pregerminated seeds of Ef-15, IR20-3, IR545-39, IR8-8, and IR8-1 were sown in 16-cm-tall, 15-cm-diameter plastic pots 18 Feb 1989 at Kansas State University, USA. Each pot was fertilized with 3 g 18-45-0 NPK. Seeds were sown 14 Mar, 24 Mar, 3 Apr, and 13 Apr at 30/pot.

For WN, the soil was puddled and water depth after sowing kept at 3 cm. For DN and DWN, soil was lightly sprinkled before sowing to keep moisture at about 80% of field capacity. After sowing, DN received 400 ml water daily. DWN received 400 ml water daily to 25, 35, 45, or 55 d after sowing (DAS), when it was submerged to 3 cm depth for 10 or 20 d before pulling seedlings. Thus, there were four seedling ages for all nursery methods and two flooding durations before pulling seedlings for DWN

At 35, 45, 55, and 65 DAS, 3 seedlings/pot were removed to measure plant fresh weight (PFW). Three fully developed leaves (second from top leaf) were excised to measure leaf water potential (LWP) with an ISSD 34693-3 pressure chamber.

DWN seedlings were as tall as those in the conventional WN and taller than those in the conventional DN. Roots were deeper and thicker and growth more vigorous than in WN or DN (see figure). DN had the highest LWP; DWN with submergence for 10 d

Seedlings of Ef-15 by WN (A), DWN (B), and DN (C) at 45 DAS. 1989.

was similar to WN (see table). Both DWN and WN showed higher PFW than DN.

DWN seedlings therefore were more vigorous than DN seedlings and used less water than WN seedlings. □